

Farmer's preferences for plant performance on rice cultivation in rainfed fields using silicate granule fertilizer in Gunungkidul of Yogyakarta

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ABSTRACT

The striking difference of productivity between irrigated rice and rainfed rice is determined some limited factor, i.e. abiotic factors, soil fertility degradation, and pest attacks. The high plant sensitivity to pests is caused by low silicates content in plant. This study aims to determine the preferences of farmers on crop performance in several rice varieties grown in rainfed lowland rice fields using several doses of granular silicate fertilizer. The research was carried out in Semanu, Gunungkidul on October 2017 to February 2018. Preference assessment was based on plant height, number of tillers, number of grain and form of grain. Preference test was conducted before harvest the plants. Based on observation of plant height and number of tillers, the plant performance showed significant differences in rice variety, silicate fertilizer, and their interaction. Based on the respondent's choices on each parameter, the preferred varieties were Ciherang (V4), Inpari Blast (V2) and Inpari 42 (V3) with the innovation of rice cultivation technology based on silicate granule fertilizer.

Keywords: *preferences, farmers, crop performance, silicates, variety*

INTRODUCTION

Rainfed rice fields are flat terraced agricultural land and emerge with water sources from rainfall. Rainfed rice fields in Gunungkidul of Yogyakarta cover an area of 44,000 ha out of a total of 117,704 ha of dry land (BPS DIY, 2015) making it possible as a food barn. The productivity of rainfed rice in Gunungkidul is averaged 4,476 kg/ha (BPS DIY, 2015), while irrigated rice is 6,300 kg/ha. The gap yield between rainfed rice and irrigated rice is very striking, as much as 1,824 kg/ha.

There are some limiting factors, namely genetic potential of low yield, high biotic factors (pests and diseases), and abiotic (drought), degradation of soil fertility and decreased production inputs, especially fertilizers (Waluyo et al., 2015). In addition, the attack of pests of disease (rice rots, blast, planthopper) is an obstacle to rice farming in rainfed rice fields. Weak plant resistance to pest attack caused by low silicate (Si) content in plants as a result of

low input of silicate elements (Makarim et al., 2007). The use of organic fertilizer and granular silicate fertilizer on rainfed dry land is a breakthrough to strengthen plant resistance from pest and disease attacks. Silicates is not included as essential nutrients, but Si fertilization can increase production, because Si could improve the physical properties of plants and affects the solubility of P in the soil. However, Silicate fertilization in rice plants in Indonesia is still very rarely done. A more comprehensive study of the use of Si in rice still needs to be done.

This study aims to determine the preferences of farmers on crop performance of some rice varieties grown in rainfed lowland rice fields with fertilizing granular silicate fertilizer as a component of cultivation technology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out in the "Sedyo Maju" Farmer Group, Pragak, Semanu, Semanu, Gunungkidul during the rainy season of 2017/2018 (October to February 2018). Site selection was determined purposively. Six rice varieties and several doses of granule silicate fertilizer were used in this study as a component of cultivation technology components in rice (Table 1).

The method used was a preference survey from 35 farmer respondents for four parameters (plant height, number of tillers, number of grain and form of grain). Preference test is done before harvesting the plants. The data obtained were analyzed using Friedman Test with a rating scale of 1 to 5. The results of the assessment were determined from the averaged value of the 5 highest / best respondents' choices. Preference test uses a preference test (hedonic test) with a level (scale) of preference 1 to 5 (1 = very dislike, 2 = dislike, and 3 = rather like, 4 = like and 5 = really like (Lamord, 1997) Data from the assessment of the level of farmers' preference were analyzed statistically further using Friedman Test (Sunyoto and Setiawan, 2013).

Table 1. Assemblies Components Technology of Rainfed Rice Cultivation

Variety	Silicate Fertilizer Dose
V1=Hibrida Hipa 9	P0 = without silicate fertilizer
V2= Inpari Blas;	P1 = 50% of recommended dose of silicate fertilizer
V3= Inpari 42,	P2 = 100% recommended dose of silicate fertilizer
V4=Ciherang;	P3 = hush ash equivalent to 100% recommended dose of silicate fertilizer)
V5=Inpari 33	P4 = 150% recommended dose of silicate fertilizer
V6= Sembada merah	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preference result which was analyzed using Friedman Test is presented in Table 2. Table 2 shows that the assessment of respondents' preferences on plant height shows a significant statistically difference which is seen from the value of Asymp.Sig. Less than 0.05. Plant performance based on observation of plant height and number of tillers refers significant differences both in the variety (V) treatment, silicate fertilizer treatment (P) and their interactions (Kristantini, 2017).

Table 2. The results of the analysis of the plant performance preference test

	Plant height	Rank	Number of tillers	Rank	Grain amount	Rank	Grain shape	Rank	Total
V1P0	15.06	17	13.44	19	16.76	14	16.38	15	
V1P1	9.06	25	11.56	23	12.30	23	14.77	20	
V1P2	19.11	8	21.50	6	19.77	8	19.82	7	
V1P3	12.98	20	13.79	18	13.65	21	15.67	18	
V1P4	17.58	13	13.92	17	16.68	15	15.91	16	
V2P0	7.50	26	7.26	30	7.24	29	6.85	30	
V2P1	16.12	16	17.18	12	15.53	16	16.52	14	
V2P2	21.70	5	22.86	4	21.80	2	20.03	6	66,36(V)
V2P3	24.29	1	23.56	3	22.89	1	22.42	2	96,16 (I)
V2P4	13.56	19	8.76	26	10.32	24	10.30	24	
V3P0	11.95	21	12.42	22	13.68	20	11.76	23	
V3P1	9.56	24	13.03	20	13.38	22	12.91	21	
V3P2	7.77	28	8.06	27	7.77	28	8.98	27	
V3P3	22.74	3	24.33	1	21.53	4	19.18	8	68,60(IV)
V3P4	16.91	14	15.94	15	16.79	13	17.39	13	
V4P0	22.11	4	22.26	5	21.61	3	22.47	1	88,45(III)
V4P1	21.08	6	19.76	8	17.03	7	20.67	5	
V4P2	16.89	15	17.55	10	15.03	17	15.86	17	
V4P3	22.82	2	24.11	2	21.39	5	21.23	3	89,55 (II)
V4P4	18.70	10	16.59	14	18.39	11	17.41	12	
V5P0	20.14	7	20.82	7	20.48	6	21.12	4	
V5P1	19.09	9	16.94	13	18.61	10	18.67	9	
V5P2	14.24	18	14.95	16	14.86	18	15.00	19	
V5P3	10.39	23	10.02	25	9.45	25	9.94	25	
V5P4	7.29	29	7.76	29	8.44	27	9.17	26	
V6P0	17.92	11	17.38	11	18.88	9	17.67	11	

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V6P1	17.70	12	17.92	9	17.03	12	17.73	10
V6P2	10.67	22	10.58	24	9.38	26	8.76	28
V6P3	13.56	19	12.86	21	14.17	19	12.05	22
V6P4	6.52	30	7.89	28	6.98	30	8.38	29
N		33		33		33		33
Chi-Square		407.20		410.13		339.62		313.38
df		29		29		29		29
Asymp. Sig.		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000

Table 3. The five best treatments based on the results of the respondents/farmers' preference test on plant performance

Rank	Treatment			
	Plant height	Number of productive tillers	Grain amount	Grain shape
1.	V2P3	V3P3	V2P3	V4P0
2.	V4P3	V4P3	V2P2	V2P3
3.	V3P3	V2P3	V4P0	V4P3
4.	V4P0	V2P2	V3P3	V5P0
5.	V2P2	V4P0	V4P3	V4P1

Based on the results of the respondent's choices in each parameter, the preferred varieties are V4 (Ciherang), V2 (Inpari Blast), V3 (Inpari 42) and V5 (Inpari 33) with rice cultivation technology innovation (Table 3). Based on silicate granule fertilizer, where the preferred fertilizer treatment sequentially is P3 (technology using husk ash as an alternative fertilizer silicate granule with an equivalent dose of 100% recommended dose of silicate), P0 (without silicate fertilizer), P2 (100% recommended dose of silicate fertilizer) and P1 (50% recommendation dose of silicate fertilizer).

According to respondents, the choice of preferences for Ciherang variety is due to the good performance of the plants (V4P3, V4P0, V4P1). The good performance of plants will be followed by high production. Besides that, the rice taste is sticky and the consumer likes it so that the farmers are used to planting Ciherang varieties. Farmers do not change easily a variety to another variety before they are convinced of its superiority (Ruskandar, 2006). The high production is the most important attribute according to farmers, because it will stimulate high income (Rahayu, 2012).

The high productivity of Ciherang varieties favored by farmers is based on results from using silicate granule fertilizer (SiO₄). In the report of the study, Kristantini (2017) stated that the genetic potential of each rice variety was

influenced by the environment of site which applied with silicate granule fertilizer. The highest productivity was achieved by Ciherang variety (8.02 t/ha) followed by Inpari 42 (7.58 t/ha).

The selection of respondent's preferences in the treatment of P3 fertilization dose (technology of using husk ash as an alternative fertilizer silicate granule with an equivalent dose of 100% recommended dose of silicate) is due to the good performance of the plants (V2P3, V4P3, V3P3) as well as the ease of obtaining husk ash among farmers. This is in accordance with the results of Kristamtini's study (2017) that a good fertilizer dosage for vegetative growth up to age 35 day after planting is P3 treatment, and the results of analysis of rice cultivation based on silicate granule fertilizer are beneficial and feasible (BC ratio and BC ratio of P1, P2, P3 and P4 > 1). The highest BC ratio and RC ratio were obtained from P3 treatment (husk ash as a natural source of granule silicate fertilizer). The BC ratio values in sequence are P3 (2.97), P1 (2.26), P2 (1.76), P0 (1.75), and P4 (1.31). While the RC ratio values are sequentially P3 (3.97), P1 (3.26), P2 (2.76), P0 (2.75), and P4 (2.31).

CONCLUSION

Rice varieties favored by farmers in cultivated rainfed rice fields using silicate fertilizer are V4 (Ciherang), V2 (Inpari Blast), V3 (Inpari 42) and V5 (Inpari 33). Farmers refer crop performance which is applied with husk ash as an alternative fertilizer silicate granule with an equivalent dose of 100% recommended dose of silicate) followed by 50% recommended dose of silicate fertilizer and 100% recommended dose of silicate fertilizer.

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